

Electrification Strategies in the Peru based in OnSSET

- Joel Nestor Vicencio Damian, Research Center of the Universidad del Pacifico, Peru
- February 1st, 2024

Keywords: Least Cost Electrification Option, LCOE, Energy Planning, OnSSET, Peru, 2030

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my sincere thanks for his dedication and support during this course to Dr. Andreas Sahlberg. His teachings have been an invaluable inspiration to me. Thank you for your commitment to education and for being an exceptional guide. In addition, I would like to express my deepest thanks to the organisers of the EMP-LAC, CCG, World Bank Group and 2050 Pathways Platform for providing me with this learning opportunity.

Executive Summary

For decades, electrification planning in developing countries has often focused on expanding the national grid to increase access to electricity. This report draws attention to the possible complementary role of decentralized alternatives - primarily microgrids - in addressing universal electricity access goals. To this end, the OnSSET model is developed for the Peruvian case and the LCOE is evaluated to compare electrification systems and choose the optimal one. The results show that with global electrification access gap of 4%, the two technologies that could provide least-cost electricity to most of Peru will be grid extension and stand-alone photovoltaic systems to achieve 100% electrification by 2030.

1. Introduction

There is universal consensus on the positive impact of electrification on economic development and quality of life. According to Cabraal, Barnes and Agarwal (2005), energy is closely linked to economic progress, reducing poverty. In the Peruvian case, Urrunaga and Aparicio (2012) highlight the importance of electricity and other public services in explaining regional disparities in per capita income, urging the improvement of infrastructure and its maintenance.

Peru is the third largest country in South America and with its 1,285,215.60 km² is strategically located in the South Pacific, bordering the Pacific Ocean to the west, Chile to the south, Brazil and Bolivia to the east, and Colombia and Ecuador to the north. In population terms, in 2020 the population amounts to 32.6 millions of which 79.3% and 20.7% of the population live in urban and rural areas, respectively, while 57.1%, 27.2% and 15.7% of the population live in the Coast, Andes and Amazon, respectively (INEI, 2017).

Figure 1. Geographical location of Peru.

Over the last decade, electrification in Peru increased from 82.5% in 2011 to 94.6% in 2020, with a slight drop to 93.5% in 2022. This pattern affected both urban and rural areas, with increases in both categories. Globally, Peru is found to be below the average electricity access in Latin America (98.3%) in 2021, underscoring the need for continued efforts to expand electricity access in the country and close the gap with other countries in the region.

Figure 2. Situation regarding the electricity service in Peru's population clusters (2017)

The study conducted in this report has a base year of 2020 with an electrification rate of 96.2% and 2030 as the final year with a projected population (pre-COVID) of 35.7 million with an electrification rate of 100%, i.e., the entire population will have electricity. Therefore, to contribute to modelling efforts intended to support electrification planning and the achievement of SDG7, this study uses the Open Source Spatial Electrification Toolkit (OnSSET), a GIS based tool, to investigate the conditions of achieving universal access to modern energy services in Peru by 2030.

2. Methodology

OnSSET, developed by **KTH** in 2015 with the support of several institutions, is a powerful tool that combines geospatial analysis with an electrification model in Python. It evaluates the most economical option (grid, mini-grid or off-grid) to supply electricity, considering geographical factors such as population, proximity to grids and roads, demand and renewable energy potential. OnSSET focuses on evaluating conventional and renewable technologies based on the lowest LCOE (cost per kWh). The tool compares technologies for each settlement, selecting the one that meets demand with the lowest LCOE. In addition, it considers all costs (investment, operation and maintenance) divided by the demand satisfied throughout the project. It is based on geospatial information that is processed and executed in Python for subsequent visualization in QGIS. (Jean et al., 2021; Sahlberg et al., 2023a; Pappis et al., 2021; Sahlberg et al., 2023b and Isihak, 2023).

Figure 3. The OnSSET methodological flow chart (Menghwani et al., 2020)

Dataset	Type	Year	Source	Link
Administrative Boundaries	Vector - polygon	2023	GEOGPS PERU	https://www.geogpsperu.com/p/descargas.html
Rives	Vector - Line	2023	GEOGPS PERU	https://www.geogpsperu.com/2020/10/rios-del-peru-red-hidrografica.html
High Voltage Lines	Vector - Line	2023	MINEM and Osinermin	Osinermin: https://saip.osinermin.gob.pe/SAIP-Portlet/formularioRegistro MINEM: https://pad.minem.gob.pe/SAIP_PORTAL/
Medium Voltage Lines	Vector - Line	2023		
Low Voltage Lines	Vector - Line	2023		
Transformers	Vector - Point	2023	Osinermin	https://saip.osinermin.gob.pe/SAIP-Portlet/formularioRegistro
Substations	Vector - Point	2023	Osinermin	https://saip.osinermin.gob.pe/SAIP-Portlet/formularioRegistro
National Road Network	Vector - Line	2023	MTC	https://portal.mtc.gob.pe/laipu/form/frmSaip.aspx
Departmental Road Network	Vector - Line	2023		
Neighborhood Road Network	Vector - Line	2023		
Power Generation Center	Vector - Point	2023	MINEM and Osinermin	Osinermin: https://saip.osinermin.gob.pe/SAIP-Portlet/formularioRegistro MINEM: https://pad.minem.gob.pe/SAIP_PORTAL/
Night Light	Raster	2022	VIIRS	https://eogdata.mines.edu/products/vnl/#annual_v2
Land Cover	Raster		GLC2000	https://www.diva-gis.org/gdata
DEM and slope	Raster		MINAM	https://geoservidorperu.minam.gob.pe/geoservidor/download_raster.aspx
Travel Time	Raster		Malaria Atlas	https://malariaatlas.org/
	Raster		European Comision	https://forobs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/gam/download
Population	Vector - polygon			
HDI	Vector - polygon			
Life expectancy	Vector - polygon	2003 - 2019	PNUD	https://www.ipe.org.pe/portal/indice-de-desarrollo-humano-idh/
Education year	Vector - polygon			
Family income per capita	Vector - polygon			
Monetary poverty	Vector - polygon	2018	INEI	https://www.gob.pe/institucion/inei/informes-publicaciones/3204872-mapa-de-pobreza-provincial-y-distrital-2018
Census Data	Vector - Point	2017	INEI	https://appinei.inei.gob.pe/transparencia/App/formulario1
Education centers	Vector - Point	2015-2020	MINEDU	https://escale.minedu.gob.pe/censo-escolar
Police station center	Vector - Point	2015-2020	MININTER	
Small grocery store	Vector - Point	2016	INEI	https://proyectos.inei.gob.pe/microdatos/
PBI distrital	Vector - Point	1993 - 2018	CIUP	https://view.officeapps.live.com/op/view.aspx?src=https%3A%2F%2Fforoeditorial.up.edu.pe%2Fwp-content%2Fuploads%2F2022%2F05%2FExcel_Estimaci%25C3%25B3n-del-PBI-a-nivel-subnacional.xlsx&wdOrigin=BROWSELINK

Table 1. Data sources

The first part of the Python code generates a CSV file in which the spatial data is assigned and other variables are generated for each cluster. The second part of the code calibrates the values for scenario generation.

For the present work, 5 scenarios were developed:

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
High demand	By 2030, demand will increase in both urban and rural areas. Considering that the population will be larger.	Urban = 3000 kWh/hh/year Rural = 3000 kWh/hh/year Diesel price = 1.2 USD/liter
Top-Down demand target - low	By 2030 people are moving from rural to urban areas.	Urban = 2117 kWh/hh/year Rural = 38.7 kWh/hh/year Diesel price = 1.2 USD/liter
Top-Down demand target - high	By 2030, the mobilization of people from rural to urban areas is lower.	Urban = 3000 kWh/hh/year Rural = 803 kWh/hh/year Diesel price = 1.2 USD/liter
Diesel subsidized	In 2030, the State passes a decree law that subsidizes fuel by 80%. In addition, demand from rural areas is moderate.	Urban = 3000 kWh/hh/year Rural = 803 kWh/hh/year Diesel price = 0.24 USD/liter
Lower CAPEX for Wind Systems	By 2030, the capital costs of renewable technologies (wind) decrease due to the learning curve and economy of scale.	Urban = 3000 kWh/hh/year Rural = 803 kWh/hh/year CAPEX Wind = 560 USD/kW Diesel price = 1.2 USD/liter

Table 2. Scenarios and main variables

3. Results

Scenario 1: High demand

Figure 4. Main results of scenario 1

In Peru, the Andean region and especially the Amazon region have several areas without electrification. The results of this scenario show that in 2030, considering that

rural and urban areas will have a high electricity demand, the least-cost way to electrify the Amazonian area will be with hybrid PV MG. While in the Andean zone, the least-cost alternative is the grid extension. In addition, the southern Andean zone opts for a SA PV.

Figure 5. Spatial results in scenario 1.

Scenario 2: Top-Down demand target - low

Figure 6. Main results of scenario 2.

In scenario 2, given that there will only be an increase in electricity demand from urban areas; while rural areas will have a decrease in electricity demand. The model prioritizes satisfying high demands with grid extension; while areas with lower demand will have to satisfy their demand with stand-alone and hybrid PV systems.

The results show that 27% of the new connections will be made through the SA PV. This results in a decrease in the extension of the network. The necessary investment will be 156 million USD for the SA PV and 111 million USD for the grid extension.

Figure 7. Spatial results in scenario 2.

Scenario 3: Top-Down demand target – high

Figure 8. Main results of scenario 3.

In scenario 3, there will be an increase in demand in both rural and urban areas. For this reason, the model chooses grid extension as the least-cost electrification alternative for most of the currently unelectrified settlements. This is followed by the choice of a MG PV mini-grid hybrid, which is still predominant in the Peruvian Amazon. And finally, with SA PV, which is still the least-cost option in the south of the country where there are more rural areas with lower population density. This choice as in the other scenarios is based on the comparison of the LCOE.

Figure 9. Spatial results in scenario 3.

Scenario 4: Diesel subsidized

Figure 10. Main results of scenario 4.

In scenario 4, the Peruvian government decides to subsidize the price of fuel by 80%. This decision allows autonomous systems using diesel to be preferred in some areas of the country where the distance to the road or travel time is shorter. Evidently, a lower fuel price is the decisive variable when choosing between autonomous photovoltaic and diesel systems.

Note that only 1% of the new connections are made through autonomous systems using diesel and the investment in these systems will only be less than 1%. The least-cost option will continue to be grid extension.

Figure 11. Spatial results in scenario 4.

Scenario 5: Lower CAPEX for Wind Systems

Figure 12. Main results of scenario 5.

In this scenario, the learning curve and economies of scale allow the government to reduce investment costs in wind systems. Renewable technologies, by the very fact that they are not mature technologies, are subject to their actual cost falling over time; however, the very fact that they become mature allows their manufacturing costs to fall.

The results indicate that only 0.4% of new connections are made with hybrid wind mini-grids. The investment made will be 5 million USD, which represents 0.2% of the total investments.

Figure 13. Spatial results in scenario 5.

In graphs 14 to 17 we can make a comparative analysis on the choice of the optimal systems for electrification in the 5 scenarios mentioned above. Extending the grid will be the recurrent option in the different scenarios, followed by PV systems.

Figure 14. Connected population by type of least-cost technology in the different scenarios.

Figure 15. Connections made by type of least-cost technology in the different scenarios.

Figure 16. Investment made by type of least-cost technology in the different scenarios.

Figure 17. Capacity generated by type of least-cost technology in the different scenarios.

5. Discussion:

In Peru, the gap in relation to the electrification gap in 2020 is 4%. It is then expected that by 2030 the gap will be 100% covered. With a major focus on rural areas, which, given Peru's geography, is a major challenge.

In rural areas, access to electricity is difficult and costly. Despite this, studies indicate that rural electrification improves welfare and removes obstacles to economic growth. Certainly, the magnitude of the benefits will depend on the specific type of energy

technology considered for rural electrification, and the characteristics of the area, community or household that will benefit from the process (Urrunaga et al., 2013).

It should be noted that many of the rural areas in Peru have populations of less than 2000 inhabitants; there are even rural population centers with 10 people. Therefore, in the scenarios presented in this report, it is evident that the least-cost alternative for the electrification of these areas will be to opt for autonomous and hybrid photovoltaic systems, which is aligned with the future plans of the Peruvian government as evaluated in the National Rural Electrification Plan (PNER) Period 2021 - 2023 and the Environmental Impact Assessment Framework for the Rural Electrification Project in Peru are studies that have analyzed the feasibility of electrifying rural areas with photovoltaic systems. In the scenario in which the Peruvian government decides to subsidize the price of fuel, this should be higher than 50% to be a more competitive technology than photovoltaic systems; however, its choice will be made in areas close to a road and mainly in urban areas. With regards to wind systems, the learning curve and economies of scale will allow a reduction in investment costs and it will be possible to electrify certain areas (north coast).

An OSeMOSYS model has already been developed in Peru. Then, the framework applied in this report will be able to connect with that model for a better application of the OnSSET model. Therefore, it will be possible to establish the least-cost electrification alternative given the future energy production that OSeMOSYS can provide.

The main limitation of this report was the detailed information. Although MINEM provided the most updated spatial information regarding the energy sector. The socioeconomic information with the greatest possible detail is based on the last census conducted in Peru which was in 2017, considering that the base year taken in this report is 2020, there is an information gap of 3 years, in which it is not possible to know exactly how many people and / or homes have or do not have electricity service. Another limitation is the specific costs for each electrical system, so it was decided to take the default values. Finally, all urban and rural households were assumed to have the same electricity demand target, and non-residential demand was not included.

The potential areas for spatial analysis in Peru are 3:

1. The agricultural sector. According to INEI (2012) only 1% of farmers have access to electricity through the public grid. The analysis through OnSSET with a focus on agriculture generated the Agrodem models which will be very helpful in the analysis of the electrification of the Peruvian agricultural sector.
2. The southern Peruvian Andean region has tragic winter seasons every year, affecting agriculture, livestock and people's well-being. Programs such as "Mi abrigo" (My shelter) have been created to address this problem. For the sake of

completeness, a proper analysis of the south zone and the way to electrify this zone will be very helpful.

3. The Peruvian Amazon to this day seems to work as an isolated region. Even in terms of electrification, transmission lines do not connect to this area. Electrifying this area will help to increase its GDP, which will also help to reduce poverty levels.

7. Conclusion

OnSSET is a special analysis tool that allows us to analyze the least-cost way to electrify a country/region/zone at the lowest possible cost. Being Open Source, it is flexible.

The application for the Peruvian case allows us to analyze 100% electrification with specific interest in rural areas, which, due to their geography, are areas whose investment in electrification would be enormous if there is no action plan. In Peru, there are many plans and strategies to electrify rural areas based on photovoltaic systems. This can be seen in the OnSSET results generated in this report.

As a planning strategy, the OnSSET tool will allow the Peruvian State to have an overview of the route to the universal electrification of Peru and to reach 100% of electrified people. This will increase welfare in monetary and non-monetary terms (security, education, health, industries).

References

Cabraal, R.A., Barnes, D.F. and Agarwal, S.G., 2005. Productive uses of energy for rural development. *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.*, 30, pp.117-144.

Cabraal, R.A., Barnes, D.F. and Agarwal, S.G., 2005. Productive uses of energy for rural development. *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.*, 30, pp.117-144.

Urrunaga, R. and Aparicio, C., 2012. Infraestructura y crecimiento económico en el Perú. *Revista CePal*.

https://www.inei.gob.pe/media/MenuRecursivo/publicaciones_digitaes/Est/Lib1539/cap01.pdf

Jean, W., Arcela, A., van Els, R.H., Brasil Junior, A.C., Velez Echeverry, S.M., de Miranda, A.R.S. and de Souza, J.S., 2021. A GIS for rural electrification strategies in the Brazilian Amazon. *Papers in Applied Geography*, 7(3), pp.239-255.

Sahlberg, A., Korkovelos, A., Kabongo, C., Trujillo, C., Khavari, B. and Nerini, F.F., 2023a. Attention to detail—exploring effects on technology selection in geospatial electrification modelling.

Pappis, I., Sahlberg, A., Walle, T., Broad, O., Eludoyin, E., Howells, M. and Usher, W., 2021. Influence of electrification pathways in the electricity sector of Ethiopia—policy implications linking spatial electrification analysis and medium to long-term energy planning. *Energies*, 14(4), p.1209.

Sahlberg, A., Usher, W., Pappis, I., Broad, O., Kebede, F.S. and Walle, T., 2023b. Exploring long-term electrification pathway dynamics: a case study of Ethiopia. *Discover Energy*, 3(1), p.1.

Isihak, S.R., 2023. Achieving universal electricity access in line with SDG7 using GIS-based Model: an application of OnSSET for rural electrification planning in Nigeria. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 45, p.101021.

Menghwani, V., Zerriffi, H., Korkovelos, A., Khavari, B., Sahlberg, A., Howells, M. and Mentis, D., 2020. Planning with justice: Using spatial modelling to incorporate justice in electricity pricing—The case of Tanzania. *Applied Energy*, 264, p.114749.

Urrunaga, R., Bonifaz, J.L., Aguirre Montoya, J., Aragón, G. and Jara, Ó., 2013. *Beneficios sociales de la electrificación rural: metodologías y estimaciones*. Universidad del Pacífico.

[inei.gob.pe/media/MenuRecursivo/publicaciones_digitaes/Est/Lib1057/libro.pdf](https://www.inei.gob.pe/media/MenuRecursivo/publicaciones_digitaes/Est/Lib1057/libro.pdf)

Appendices

Appendix A. Amazonas

AMAZONAS

AMAZONAS

Appendix B. Apurimac

APURIMAC

APURIMAC

Appendix C. Ayacucho

AYACUCHO

Appendix D. Cajamarca

CAJAMARCA

CAJAMARCA

Appendix E. Cusco

CUSCO

CUSCO

Appendix F. Loreto

Appendix G. Madre de Dios

MADRE DE DIOS

MADRE DE DIOS

Appendix H. Puno

PUNO

PUNO

Appendix I. San Martin

SAN MARTIN

SAN MARTIN

Appendix J. Ucayali

Appendix K. Key Data Assumptions

Modelling period & Targets	Parameter	Value	Unit
	Start year	2020	year
	End year	2030	year
	Current national electricity access rate	96.20%	percentage
	- Urban elec. rate	99.00%	percentage
	- Rural elec. rate	86.10%	percentage
	Target access rate in end year	100.00%	share
Population data			
	Total population (start year)	32,625,948	
	Urban pop ratio (start year)	0.783	
	Rural pop ratio (start year)	0.217	
	Pop growth rate	96%	percentage
	Total population (end year)	35,792,079	
	Urban pop ratio (end year)	0.783	
	Rural pop ratio (end year)	0.217	
	Urban Household size	3.46	people/HH
	Rural Household size	2.48	people/HH
Technology specs & costs			
Centralized Grid	Grid generating cost	0.047	USD/kWh
	Expected CAPEX of power plants	2000	USD/kW
	Annual Cap on New Grid Capacity	140	MW/year
	Annual Cap on New Grid Connections	52,000	connections/year
T&D	Transmission losses	10.00%	percentage
	Distribution losses	8.00%	percentage
	T&D Operation & Maintenance cost	3.00%	
	HV line type	66	kV
	Indicative HV line cost	180,000	USD/km
	MV line type	11 or 33	kV
	Indicative MV line cost	50,000	USD/km
	Max MV line stretch	50	km
	LV line type	0.24	kV
	lv_line_cost	no data	USD/km
	Max Lv line stretch	0.8	km
	HV to MV transformer cost	no data	USD/unit
	MV to LV transformet cost	15,000	USD/unit
	Service transformer type	50	kVa
	Service transformer cost	no data	USD/unit
	Max no of connections per service transformer	300	connections
	Service drop / connection cost	no data	USD/con
Mini grids			
Diesel generator	Diesel pump price	1.2	USD/liter
	Diesel generator cost	378	USD/kVA
	Diesel generator life	10	years

	Diesel generator O&M cost	10.00%	percentage
PV	PV module cost	1147	USD/kW
	PV panel life	25	years
	PV O&M cost	1.50%	percentage
Wind	Wind turbine cost	2800	USD/kW
	Wind turbine life	20	years
	Wind turbine O&M cost	1.50%	percentage
Hydro	Small scale hydro (indicative) cost	3000	USD/kW
	Small scale hydro life	30	years
	Small scale hydro O&M cost	1.50%	percentage
BoS (for mini grids)	Battery cost	427	USD/kWh
	Inverter cost	608	USD /kW
	Inverter life	10	years
	Charge/Discharge efficiency of battery	0.92	percentage
	Maximum depth of discharge of battery	0.8	percentage
	Charge controller	142	USD/unit
	Maximum loss of load	0.50%	percentage
	Service drop / connection cost	50	USD/con
Solar Home Systems	SHS costs classification		
	< 0.02 kW	9,620	USD/kW
	0.02-0.05 W	8,780	USD/kW
	0.05-0.1 W	6,380	USD/kW
	0.1-1 W	4,470	USD/kW
	> 1 kW	6,950	USD/kW
	SHS life	15	years
	SHS O&M	1.50%	percentage
Other			
	Discount rate	8.00%	percentage
Demand Targets			
Residential sector	Total estimated demand in 2030	573	GWh
	Target Demand for Urban settlements	103	kWh/cap/year
	Target Demand for Rural settlements	5	kWh/cap/year
Social infrastructure			
Health facilities	Total estimated demand in 2030	45	GWh
	Service level 1	2,740	kWh/year/facility
	Service level 2	5,500	kWh/year/facility
	Service level 3	9,130	kWh/year/facility
Education facilities	Total estimated demand in 2030	109	GWh
	Primary	730	kWh/year/facility
	Secondary	2,810	kWh/year/facility

